

THE ROLE OF TRANSLATION IN TEACHING FL

Abdullayev Asqar Abduhakimovich
Teacher of SamSIFL

Abstract. *Translation is the communication of the meaning of a source-language text by means of an equivalent target-language text. This article describes the role of translation in teaching foreign languages. Additionally, there is given some types and usage of them.*

Key words: *translation, simultaneous, diachronic, adequate, free, literary translation.*

Today, one of the main requirements for high professional qualifications is perfect knowledge of foreign languages. It is not for nothing that special attention is paid to learning English, which has been taking a leading place among the languages of international communication. In the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, English language teaching and learning is rising to a new level of quality based on the scientific approach and the introduction of new information and communication and pedagogical technologies that fully meet the requirements of the time. Since learning a foreign language is a requirement of the present time, developing new methods of language learning for the young generation based on the "National Personnel Training Program" and recommending them to the study process is one of the urgent issues facing scientists and specialists. In order for our talented young people to become mature specialists in their fields of interest, first of all, it is necessary for them to have a perfect knowledge of a foreign language, including English. There are many methods for learning English, and the choice depends on which way they learn the language faster and more effectively. One such effective way is to learn a language through translation. A lot of works have been written in the scientific literature about the theory of translation, types of translation,

and the issue of its operation. Translation is a type of activity that teaches the activity of translation. Translation is the conversion of information, text, speech from one language to another. By translation we understand the translation of text, speech and speech of another language into the language being studied. Translation is necessary and necessary in teaching English, it has a lot of benefits and importance.

Translation helps to consciously understand unfamiliar information given in the target language, information that is difficult to understand in English.

Translation usually takes two forms, oral and written. Among these, translation is further divided into types:

1. Simultaneous translation;
2. Diachronic translation;
3. Adequate translation;
4. Free translation;
5. word by word translation;
6. Literary translation.

Synchronous translation means translating a speech or text while listening to the speaker, while diachronous translation means listening to, reading, and then translating the speech or lecture that has been listened to. In word-for-word translation, the text and speech are translated without changing the place and meaning of the words. Literary translation is mainly used in the translation of literary works, poems, stories, novels, it is quite complicated.

It is necessary to know in advance the place, usefulness and necessity of using translation in teaching English, and then it is better to use it. Improper and frequent use of translation has a detrimental effect on English language teaching.

We can see that the use of translation and its application in teaching English has a positive effect in the following cases:

- ✓ In opening the meaning of the English lexicon. In this case, the lexicon is used if there is only one translation equivalent. If the meaning of the lexicon is wider or narrower in one language, an explanation is given to the translation;
- ✓ Knowing and explaining the meaning of English grammar material;

- ✓ Teaching listening comprehension in English, checking information and understanding;
- ✓ Checking the reading and understanding of the text;
- ✓ Listening to someone else's speech and learning to translate;
- ✓ When studying the constructions of some sentences in the text, sentences that are not structured according to the rules, paragraphs that are difficult to understand;
- ✓ Teaching translation from Uzbek to English or from English to Uzbek.

In addition, in teaching foreign languages, the acquisition of grammar rules through translation is also envisaged. That is, in this case, the teacher explains the grammar rule to the students orally, and then the students are asked to translate those rules in writing. Because during the translation process, students focus on the meaning of each word and try to understand the general meaning of the text. This process allows students to increase their vocabulary, develop their translation skills, and at the same time teach them to understand the grammatical structure of words.

Therefore, translation plays a very important role in the process of language learning and mainly develops students' translation literacy along with learning a foreign language.

Used literature:

1. A.K. Kuchiboyev “Xorijiy tillarga o’rgatishning kommunikativ metodikasi” Samarqand:. 2010 143b
2. J. Jalolov “English teaching methodics” T:. 1996 367b
3. O’. Hoshimov, I.Yoqubov “English teaching methodics“ T:. – 2003 300b
4. Alisherovna, M. N., Furqatovna, S. Y., & kizi, K. Z. K. (2022). Principles for determining the categories of proximity of the Russian language to Uzbek in the field of phraseology: Identification of interlingual phraseological accordance. *International Journal of Health Sciences*, 6(S5), 1414²1419.
5. Абдувахабова У. Экспрессивно-стилистические и художественные особенности авторского стиля герберта бейтса //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2021. – №. 3 (80). – С. 28-33.

6. Ibodullayeva M. H. The use of superstitions in the life of English speaking countries and their types according to situations //Samarkand: So'z san'ati. – 2022. – С. 2-3.
7. Karimova S. V. Strategies for expanding students' vocabulary in ESL lessons //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 730-736.
8. Назарова Н. Б. ЭРТАКНИНГ ДИСКУРСИВ БЕЛГИЛАРИ //МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА. – 2022. – Т. 5. – №. 2.
9. Пулатова Ф. А. Талабаларни танқидий фикрлашга ўргатиш ва педагогик ёндашиш //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 822-825.
10. Furkatovna S. Y. Modern methods and approaches for effective distance learning of English language //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 500-504.
11. Khamraeva Z. K. The problem with the four conditionals or causality in english //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 10. – С. 1428-1433.
12. Bakhodirovna K. F. The Importance of TPR (Total Physical Response) Method in Teaching English for beginners //Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching. – 2022. – Т. 8. – С. 156-158.
13. Холикова Л. Ф. MANAGING UNIVERSITY STUDENTS'RESEARCH SKILLS THROUG INTERDISCIPLINARY PROJECTS AND E-PROJECTS //МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 4.
14. Kholmurodovna K. D., Valievna K. S. DEVELOPING SPEAKING ABILITIES OF LEARNERS BY ENRICHING THEIR VOCABULARY OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE //Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 09. – С. 6-10.